

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS VOLUME 16 (2023)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

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Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2023,
vol. 16

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

RESPONSIBLE LEADERSHIP AND ACCOUNTABILITY CHALLENGE IN NIGERIA'S PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: A GLOCALISED PERSPECTIVE.

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Abstract

While considering the idea of glocalisation, responsible leadership as a matter of importance must be characterized by innovation and social engineering. Also, Nigeria's leadership and public accountability questions, problems and allied negativities must be scientifically understood in order to attain sustainable development. The reason for this is that Nigeria in recent times is fraught with divergent leadership challenges which have made the attainment of sustainable development overtly impossible. Therefore, with heavy emphasis on qualitative research approach, the study sets out to interrogate prerequisites for responsible leadership and accountability in Nigeria's public administration and sustainable development; implications for responsible leadership and accountability challenge in Nigeria's public administration and sustainable development. The study revealed inter alia that responsible leadership and accountability challenge encouraged loss of money in Nigeria and so on. It therefore concluded that, responsible leadership accountability challenge in the Nigeria's public administration grossly affects sustainable development. The study recommended periodic briefing of the electorate with regard to the functionalities of government and its agencies as a way forward.

Keywords: Accountability; Glocalisation; Principal-Agent Theory; and Sustainable Development.

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Introduction

Arguably, Nigeria has both in the past and present had responsible and irresponsible leadership bedeviled by accountability challenges of different sort. The reason for this is that third world countries' leaders see themselves as being above the law. In simple term, the law does not apply to such egocentric leaders in public organizations and the federation in general as it ought to. Logically, "If law does not apply, it cannot control (Chan & Rosenbloom, 2010:15)." It follows then that the dearth of responsible and accountable leadership have in most cases reared its ugly head against the attainment of a glocally managed society here and/or there within Africa's region, which Nigeria has been worst damaged by its ebb and flow. Questions about responsible leadership and accountability in public administration remain problematic in this period where attention has been shifted from Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). As such, the problem of accountability is amongst the prominent challenges in contemporary leadership in Nigeria. The reason for this may have been aptly captured by National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) (2004:50) when it stated that, "Once any organization is in government hands, there is bound to be questions about its accountability. In theory, all parts of government are accountable to the political leadership and finally to the people." Suffice it to say that; in practice, the issue of leadership and accountability has been relegated to the back and glocalisation in carrying out leadership functions also treated with a wave of hand. Concerning the idea of glocalisation in the context of this paper; responsible leadership as a matter of importance must be characterized by innovation and social engineering that aligns with local needs while considering international best practices. This is where Africa's Economies like Nigeria have failed and must be succinctly re-engineered to incorporate both the outside and the inside. Then, what are the outside and the inside? The outside is apparently the global guidelines and principles, which must be tailored to suit the locality where it is imported into – the inside. To get it right, "Sustainable development requires better scientific understanding of the problems (McKeown, 2002:9)." Therefore, Nigeria's leadership and public accountability questions, problems and allied negativities must be scientifically understood in order to attain sustainable development. The reason for this is that Nigeria is fraught with divergent leadership challenges which have made the attainment of sustainable development overtly impossible in recent

times in various component units of Nigeria and other climes in the world. This aptly captures the need for this study.

Significantly; it should be noted that, "Life is challenge. Every new day throws up its own challenges. But through it all even in the transformation continuum (though there be differentia of rate/pace/speed) there are the basics. There are standards. There is need for dynamism as well as stability. There is need for focus (Udenta, 2007:312). What are the basics that must be followed? What are the standards that have prompted the need for such focus? This study sees globalization and glocalization as the basics/standards that must be focused on and meticulously followed. In respect to this, public policy makers in Nigeria should formulate policies that suit current international best practices. This is where globalisation comes into play. Indeed, "Generally, globalization is seen as a process of reducing barriers between countries and of encouraging closer economic, political and social interaction which could vastly increase the ability of people everywhere to share knowledge about living standards. Globalization is a process and a means to achieve the goals of globalism (Sapru, 2013:580)." While we think globally, Nigeria is expected to look into the varied domestic social values and implement them yet in line with international standard so as to have a glocalised polity ready to be re-engineered towards sustainable development.

The problem is that the leadership over the years has neglected the peculiar social, political cum economic milieus associated with Nigeria. Then again, the Nigerian problem is no doubt hinged upon leadership. Achebe (1983:10) in supporting this perspective submitted that; "Nigerians are what they are only because their leaders are not what they should be." The paper aligns with the preceding view of Achebe (1983); because perfect leadership is leadership by example. Considering recent happenings and the calibre of leaders that Nigeria parades; it is clear that change is vital at the moment. The change Nigeria needs is a replacement or shift from the status quo (Chioke, 2017). Thus, the need for a paradigm shift loudly calls for an accentuated attention and presto-chango in the country's policy implementation strategies.

Abonyi (2005:61) says, "An organization exists not in a vacuum, but mutually dependent on its external environment. It is a part of larger system, the industry to which it belongs and society. Thus, the enterprise receives inputs, transforms them and exports the outputs to the environment..." The input received is better transformed by responsible leadership, but where none is existing, it becomes an

issue to the general system – Nigeria and even beyond. Meanwhile, “Despite a plethora of development policies and programmes instituted over the past four decades, and its enormous materials and human resources, Nigeria remains a socio-economically undeveloped country (NEPAD, 2008:1).” Why? In some cases, it is truly a matter of lack of responsible leadership. Also, the reason could be attributed to accountability challenge associated with responsible leadership exemplified in its posture of no or little accountability to the electorate. Therefore, responsible leadership and the problem of accountability in the bureaucratic structure and/or public administration of Africa’s economies like Nigeria have guaranteed: unethical behaviours, lack of innovation, loss of money, and so on. The focus of this paper is to examine the prerequisites for responsible leadership and accountability in Nigeria’s public administration and sustainable development from a glocal backdrop.

Addressing the Conceptual Framework from a Glocal Viewpoint Responsible Leadership

Social sciences must be context sensitive but not context dependent (Khondker, 2004:4). In light of this, the paper begins by defining separately the two terms – a) Responsible and b). Leadership. Responsible means, “Having the job or duty of doing something or taking care of somebody/something, so that you may be blamed if something goes wrong. To have to report to somebody/something with authority or in a higher position and explain to them what you have done (Hornby, 2005:1002).” In differentia, leadership is “the state or position of being a leader (Hornby, 2005:672).” To start with, to lead is to be a leader and leadership entails leading. Leadership or being a leader is more of directing others (Chioke, 2012:112). While I stand to be corrected; leadership from a global dimension entails planning the will of the state (public policies), budgeting the amount of materials and money needed for the execution of the will of the state, organizing via the establishment of structures in form of interrelated functions and determination of the activities required for the attainment of the will of the state, directing by continuous task of making decisions and embodying those decisions into the general order and interest of the state, coordinating by bringing together different parts of the general order/interest and the human resources involved in it and reporting the activities attained and those yet to be attained to the appropriate authority usually the electorate. In Nigeria, the story is however different and appalling. From our corrupted viewpoint, leadership is all about occupying a political office,

theoretically dishing out instructions on what should be done and then looting the public treasury. To the shame of these ravenous wolves that occupy hallowed seats at the Federal, State and Local government levels, leadership is beyond this. It is about shunning corruption and not pretending to be shunning corruption while wallowing in obnoxious practices.

In this dimension, it suffices to say that leadership is action oriented. Then again, Grahame (2016:2) was right to opine that, "If leadership is action then responsible leadership is responsible action. Responsible leadership is taking responsible action." Shi and Ye (2016:878) posit that, "...responsible leadership weighs and balances diverse claims from all stakeholders in accordance with the code of ethics, then makes efforts to build and maintain lasting and trustful relationships with stakeholders, aiming to achieve sustainable development of corporate and society." Responsible leadership is aimed at building mutually beneficial relationships with stakeholders inside and outside organization through carrying out corporate social responsibility actively, in order to realize mutual benefits and shared goals (Song, Sun and Wei, 2009:988). What about capacity building and mentorship? Within the purview of the current debate, the researcher maintains that, a glocally minded leadership focuses on capacity building via training in line with international standards of education and geared toward mentoring the entirety of its followership via proper orientation.

Importantly, a responsible leader is to a greater extent a transparent leader and as such, transparency is required for responsible leadership to be in place. Also, it could be averred that transparency is needed to make accountability workable. Thus, transparency is multifaceted. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2001:3) opines that, "A system is transparent when all relevant information on the budget is made available in both a timely and systematic manner."

From a glocal viewpoint, this paper is of the view that responsible leadership entails making and enforcing sustainable development blueprints, which agree with the globally acclaimed Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by taking into cognizance local needs and considering the interests of all citizens in the country irrespective of social stratification. Bearing these premises raised in mind, responsible leadership is herein again operationalised as government at any level that is transparent, accountable to the people that elected it and responsive to local needs while maintaining international best practice in its public administration processes.

However, Voegtlin (2011:59) sees responsible leadership in this context means that leaders have to recognize (moral) problems by considering the consequences of their decisions or actions for all possibly affected constituencies. They should then use their influence to incorporate stakeholder groups into the decision-making process by providing arenas for discussion and dialogue. The arguments are evaluated from the perspectives of all affected stakeholders. The responsible leader thereby advocates arguments that emphasise the point of view of the organization. Further, he or she tries to achieve a consensus among the participants by weighing and balancing the different interests. He further stated that, responsible leadership represents a continuum, ranging through non-responsible leadership, which can be characterized as self-interested, egoistic leadership behavior acting solely on an instrumental rationale, to the responsible leader acting according to the ideal presented above (Voegtlin, 2011:59). Responsible leadership is one built on appropriate responses on significant areas of responsibilities. This kind is one that takes responsibility for actions whether good or bad. From this, one could authoritatively say that blame game politicians are not responsible leaders. It becomes imperative to note that responsible leadership is accountable leadership. Hence, where there is no responsible leadership, accountability goes into extinction.

Accountability: A Conceptual Dissection

The notion of accountability as used in this study is same with public or political accountability. While this is the point here, Okoli (2011) cited in (Osuebi, Nwachukwu, Arinze & Nnadi, 2019:24) sees, political accountability as a variant of public accountability. However, for the purpose of this study, the phenomena – accountability, public accountability and political accountability are interchangeably used. Political accountability according to Basse (2014) as cited in Osuebi, et al (2019:24) is the accountability of government, civil servant and politicians to the public and to the legislative bodies such as congress or parliament. Additionally, it has been argued that, “Political accountability is the accountability of the government, civil servants and politicians to the public and to legislative bodies such as congress or a parliament.” The just cited definitions aptly captured the true sense of accountability. It becomes imperative to state that, “Political Accountability is a fundamental feature in any effective public administrative system. It presupposes that all governmental departments have to be efficient because they have to ensure value for tax payers’ money (Osuebi, et al 2019:24).” Therefore, it becomes

germane to state that Okoli (2011) cited in Osuebi, et al (2019:24) aptly relayed the point as follows: “Political accountability means that political office holders are accountable and answerable to the people. When this happens, they become the servants and not the masters of the people. They respond to the yearnings, demands and aspirations of the people, thereby promoting good governance.” This is where principal – agent theory surfaces in this enquiry; because political accountability in this paper is about rendering an account cum being held accountable. This is the missing mark of responsible leadership in third world countries like Nigeria.

This paper therefore contends that; accountability, the obligation imposed by law, regulation and lawful order on political office holders and bureaucrats must be fostered and maintained by all sovereign states in Africa and the world at large. Why? Krishna (2010) cited in Sapru (2013:516) may have captured the reasons thus, “accountability is the prerequisite for preventing abuse of delegated power by the ministries and public servants. Any breakdown in the process of accountability is liable to lead to effective, corrupt and irresponsible rule.” Developgoodhabits.com (2019:1) reinforced, “accountability requires two parts: internal control and external support. Being personally responsible for your results is important, but it’s not enough to achieve peak performance. You need that external accountability to keep you on track.” At this juncture, the internal control as stated above is equally of two aspects: internal control by oneself and internal control by the internal environment of the organization. Then, the external support is the outside observer or the general public that such person is answerable to.

The Concept of Sustainable Development

Sustainable development herein connotes all attempts at preserving or conserving varied resources for the future. The notion of ‘future’ as operationalised above suggests that sustainable development is and should be treated as a long term plan. To corroborate this, “The overall goal of sustainable development (SD) is the long-term stability of the economy and environment; this is only achievable through the integration and acknowledgement of economic, environmental, and social concerns throughout the decision making process (Emas, 2015:2).” Vander-Merwe & Van-der-Merwe (1999:1) defined it thus, “Sustainable development is a program that changes the economic development process to ensure the basic quality of life, protecting valuable ecosystems and other communities at the same time.” Hence, to sustainably develop, no community should be found

destroying another and must not be allowed to do so. In this dimension, the paper directly points out the need to curtail the inhuman activities of Boko Haram sect in Northern Nigeria and the Fulani herdsmen's nefarious actions against the Southern and Western communities as such dastardly activities negate the concept of sustainable development in the context of the just cited literature.

In achieving sustainable development, decision making is very important and must be given due consideration. It is thus believed that, "The key principle of sustainable development underlying all others is the integration of environmental, social, and economic concerns into all aspects of decision making (Emas, 2015:3)." Additionally, "The point, rather, is that all other principles and concepts in the sustainable development framework have integrated decision-making at their foundation, and that integrated decision-making provides the glue that holds them together. Without integrated decision-making, sustainable development is simply an odd assortment of unrelated principles (Dernbach, 2003:258)." To advance this course, the researcher emphasize that: The problem envisageable herein is that the leadership over the years has neglected the peculiar social, political cum economic milieus associated with Nigeria. To this effect, "It is this deeply fixed concept of integration that distinguishes sustainability from other forms of policy (Emas, 2015:3)." Nevertheless, "In practice, sustainable development requires the integration of economic, environmental, and social objectives across sectors, territories, and generations. Therefore, sustainable development requires the elimination of fragmentation; that is; environmental, social and economic concerns must be integrated throughout decision making processes in order to move towards development that is truly sustainable (Emas, 2015:3)." In this regard, sustainable development is geared towards integration of important factors capable of ensuring social stability and re-engineering for future generations.

There is no development to sustain, because what is obtainable here in Nigeria is no development. With respect to this, Nigeria has not witnessed development in the true sense of development when viewed from a global perspective. In short, Nigeria is not yet developed and nothing more pretentious than this. Importantly, "Sustainable development should provide a solution in terms of meeting basic human needs, integrating environmental development and protection, achieving equality, ensuring social self-determination and cultural diversity, and maintaining ecological integrity (Tomislav, 2018:87)." However, this description is not the real picture of what is

obtainable here and therefore could be regarded as utopian in Nigeria public space. In Nigeria are there are instances of divisions, ethnic chauvinism, fragmentations, divide and rule policies, religious bigotry/intolerance, Boko Haram insurgencies, power failure, attempts towards rugarisation of component states for cattle rearing business of the Northern elites, herdsmen attack on helpless farmers, attendant extreme hunger, difficulty in accessing basic needs, manipulation or outright disregard for federal character principle, dirty politicking, and other leadership questions.

The truth remains that no one can talk about preserving or conserving for the future yet unseen amidst extreme hunger. Therefore, the foregoing positions of the researcher is directly or indirectly aligned with Vare & Scott (2007:191) viewpoint as follows: "Sustainable development is a process of changes, where resources are raised, the direction of investments is determined, the development of technology is focused and the work of different institutions is harmonized, thus the potential for achieving human needs and desires is increased as well." Consequent upon this, Emas (2015:3) was right to have posited that, "sustainable development requires the elimination of fragmentation..."

Theoretical Framework

To advance this study, the paper adopts Principal – Agent Theory (PAT). From a historical point of view, it has been said that, "The principal and agent theory emerged in the 1970s from the combined disciplines of economics and institutional theory. There is some contention as to who originated the theory, with theorists Stephen Ross and Barry Mitnick claiming its authorship (Mitnick, 2006)." The advocates of this theory maintain that the modern democratic state is based on a set of principal-agent relationships in the public sector (Sapru, 2013:427). These relationships have in one form or the other influenced the thinking on leadership in various forms. For example, it involves the relationships that exist between leaders and the masses. This has informed the choice of anchoring the study upon this theory, because every responsible leadership (Agent) relates with the masses (Principal).

Figure 1: Diagram showing Principal and Agent relationship

Source: Author's description

With regard to this study, the Principal is the public, while the Agent(s) is/are the chief executive, politicians and bureaucrats. Sapru (2013:430) contends that, "The principal-agent structure of the state is characterized by ambiguity, opportunistic behavior, moral hazard, and adverse selection. This sort of structure does not prevent the agent from reversing the relationship and regarding itself as the principal." This is the bane of Nigeria and other African economies. "The theory of principal and agent suggests that accountability problems are inherently worse in the public sector and in public enterprise in particular. This means that poor accountability is a justification for privatization in addition to the economic rationale set out earlier (NOUN, 2004:12)." This being the truth, it has remained enigmatic for political office holders to be accountable to the electorate. In other words, Nigeria is fraught with responsible leadership and accountability challenge. Hence, there is need to examine its implications while addressing matters arising with respect to responsible leadership and accountability challenges from a global perspective.

It has always been an issue for conscious scrutiny whether or not the agent is running and actually meeting the principal's set targets. Thus, to have a responsible leadership that would sustainably develop the country, it is expected that the values of real democracy should be adequately inculcated by creating conducive atmosphere for unity and collective will to be manifestly pursued and attained. At this juncture, it should be noted that:

The easier it is for the public to understand what members of the government are doing, the more accountable the public will hold the politicians. This accountability strengthens the first set of principals (public) and agents (elected politicians). It also brings in the public as a monitor to check the second set of principals (elected politicians) and agents (bureaucrats). If agents are doing what principals want, there should be better budget performance (Sapru, 2013:429).

Suffice it to say that, when there is budget performance, responsible leadership is in place and accountability would be easily rendered as it is difficult and rare for one to render account of what has not been discharged. Therefore, what makes leaders not to be accountable is when there is zero performance. The point is that when one has manifestly and judiciously executed a task, one readily and eagerly renders account, but when the reverse is the case, the agent finds it uncomfortable for the principal to demand stewardship let alone being compelled to act accordingly. He (agent) will therefore corruptly evade accounting for his stewardship. That is where irresponsible leadership surfaces.

In applying this theory, the researcher notes that a responsible principal will guarantee ethical behaviours, visible innovations, zero tolerance to loss of money, sustainable development etc and vice versa. In the present case of Nigeria, the agent(s) is/are usually not running the will of the state in keeping with the needs, dictates and demands of the electorate (principal). This is where glocalisation comes into play in this enquiry by identifying the prerequisites for responsible leadership and accountability in the country's public administration and sustainable development.

Prerequisites for Responsible Leadership and Accountability in Nigeria's Public Administration and Sustainable Development: Addressing the Obstacles from a Glocalised Parallax.

Considering the need to have a glocally managed society, the following are considered prerequisites for the glocalisation of the country's leadership/public administration:

Rule of law – Simply put, rule of law is rule according to the law. Sapru (2013:585-586) contends that:

This means that the citizens are legally protected from the arbitrary or capricious actions by public authorities. The rule of law is based on the enterprise of independent judiciary. The legal order that is established on this foundation serves to regulate relations between individuals and groups within a society as well as between individuals and groups within a society as well as between individuals and

groups within a society as well as between citizens and state (pp.585 – 586).

When there is rule of law, the leaders are held accountable for their actions and inactions. Through this, sustainable development would be attained. It is however regrettable that in Nigeria, rule of law is far from the routine practices and this has plunged the country into severe underdevelopment. Nigeria while adhering to international laws must learn to hold her leaders responsible in terms of keeping and upholding domestic laws and the entirety of her grundnorm. The inability to do so generates the problem of accountability in Nigeria and must be corrected as quick as possible.

Political Participation – In Nigeria, there is high rate of political apathy which has snowballed into various leadership ordeals. Pertinently, political participation is the cornerstone for a democratic society. It then appears that political participation is closely associated with society-centred approach. This is because when citizens participate in the determination of the dividends of democracy or contribute either immensely or considerably to the mobilization of human resources needed for socio-economic cum political programs of the State, there is political participation and governance of such sovereign entity is said to be society-centred. Imperatively, Sapru (2013) was right to have emphasized that:

In a democracy, as distinct from an autocracy, governance should be 'society centred.' It would include the government, which is its dominant part, based on transparency, the private sector and the civil society. All three are critical sustaining human, economic and social development. The government creates a conducive political, legal and living environment. The private sector promotes enterprise and generates job and income. The civil society facilitates interaction by mobilizing groups to participate in economic, social and political activities.

Bearing the aforesaid position in mind, the leadership and/or administrators of African polities and Nigeria in particular should run a society centred and all inclusive governance demonstrated through political participation from a glocalised standpoint - in line with global principles and local values.

Merit System – Over the years, public administration cum the determination of who gets what has been erroneously based on nepotism, favouritism, ethnocentrism and other unethical standards. These just mentioned parameters are not within the purview of international best practices. It then suffices to aver that institutional recruitment and selection processes should be based on merit. From

a global viewpoint, “employment into the civil service is based on technical qualifications (Chioke, 2012:88).” But to attain sustainable development, a responsible leadership ought to consider the use of qualified and available local manpower in the recruitment processes into her bureaucracies. This is where glocalisation comes into play in part of discourse.

For the leadership to be responsible and accountable to the public, merit system remains a veritable instrument. Therefore, sustainable development is conditioned via priority placed upon credible as well as creditable arrangements for global best practices, which meritocracy is part of them.

Commitment – The level of commitment that leaders have determines how far sustainable development plans/strategies will go. In this dimension; development whether rural or urban requires commitment for it to be sustained. Udentia (2011:144) reiterates that, “All in all, commitment calls for appropriate attitudinal dispositions as well as the ability to make sacrifices, if and when occasion calls for such. As every true captain knows, come what may, the captain is the first to enter the craft and the last to exit. That is commitment.” This is the expected normal that responsible captains (leaders) should apply. Considering global standard/feature and the need to further current local needs, commitment is herein seen as being sacrosanct as well as a prerequisite for responsible leadership, accountability and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Political/Government Accountability – Meanwhile, “At the core of political accountability is the need for rigorous systems of financial administration with swift and tough penalties for malfeasance. The political commitment to establish honest and effective systems of administrative accountability can be achieved only through an effective system of political accountability and a sound judicial system (Sapru, 2013).” The performance of this will consequently give room for a responsible leadership and sustainable development in Nigeria and even beyond.

Responsible Leadership and Accountability Challenge: Implications for Nigeria’s Public Administration and Sustainable Development

There is no gainsaying that the problem of leadership lacuna is currently troubling some African economies like Nigeria. To corroborate this we glean as follows: “Everywhere we look, from our companies, to our institutions and governments I see a leadership gap, a gap between what is needed and what is provided. Instead of getting what we need we seem to have to put up with the opposite. Again and again we are confronted with stories of leaders who have

lined their own pockets or whose private lives expose a wide, hypocritical gap with their public persona and stated positions (Grahame, 2016:2).” The leadership lacuna that exists in several economies in Africa and Nigeria to be exact is what responsible leadership and accountability will cushion if properly fostered and consolidated. Unfortunately, there is the problem of responsible leadership and accountability in virtually all sectors of this country. This implies that the country will continue to soar in underdevelopment.

Accountability in leadership is vital for the overall achievement of responsible leaders. Available literature on responsible leadership suggests that, “People make better choices and perform at a higher level when they know they are being watched by others. The reasoning is simple – when you are held accountable for your actions, you will work harder (developgoodhabits.com).” However, when there are no watchdogs, decrease in service delivery/productivity thus becomes the implication of responsible leadership and accountability problem in public administration process of a sustainable development based polity.

Being a responsible leader has a correlation with accountability and accountability compels responsible leaders to closely examine and re-examine each stated objective of the corporate body/polity. Through this, the best course of action with regard to such objective is guaranteed. When this is done, the drive towards a better public administration and sustainable development is birthed and well groomed to meet up with the leadership task. In Nigeria, the reverse appears to be the gargantuan issue facing development.

Accountability ensures commitment. During gubernatorial or presidential campaigns, candidates often come up with good and sustainable development blueprints, but rarely do that good development blueprints in form of party manifesto last beyond post election days or a year in office. Such candidate usually gets sidetracked as he basks in the euphoria of being in control of state apparatus and quickly forgets about continuing with the stated will/goal of the state, which is more often than not a development strategy. With regard to public administration and sustainable development, accountability “...forces you to follow through on commitments (developgoodhabits.com).” In the same vein, Voegtlin, Patzer, and Scherer (2012:6) contend that, responsible leadership can motivate and promote employees’ to organizational commitment. At this point, the nexus between responsible leadership and unethical behavior(s). To start with, Kaptein (2008:978) argues that, “Unethical

behaviors usually refer to some behaviors which can't be recognized and accepted by the public." It becomes vital to aver that responsible leadership greatly reduces unethical behaviours and its attendant challenges in government bureaucracies. However, where this is lacking it portends serious threats to public administration and sustainable development. Specifically, the implication of responsible leadership and accountability challenge in Nigeria is the increase in unacceptable organizational behaviours.

Conclusion

The study has shown the prerequisites for responsible leadership and sustainable development in Nigeria. With regard to responsible leadership and accountability, the study has also established the implications for public administration and sustainable development. As a concluding remark, it should be noted that responsible leadership and accountability challenge in the public administration of Nigeria's economy/polity grossly affects sustainable development. Hence, there is need for the application of the remedial measures below and utter renaissance of the country's bureaucratic and political terrains. In order to ensure political participation and accountability; this study therefore recommends periodic briefing of the electorate with regard to the functionalities of government and its agencies. This would make these terrains to have public accountability alignment.

The findings of the study have far reaching implications on the stakeholders at all levels of government in Nigeria. The implication of this study/finding is hinged upon the fact that; in spite of the myriad of existing development policies, human and material resources, Nigeria is yet socio-economically underdeveloped and does not at the moment show any tangible trappings of sustainable development. The reason for this anomaly could be attributed to lack of responsible leadership that is accountable to the electorate. Meanwhile, if Nigeria remains socio-economically underdeveloped, how can we talk about sustainable development? Truly, it becomes imperative to state that one cannot talk about sustainable development in such situation; because there is little or virtually nothing to sustain. Hence, despite the many years of independence Nigeria is still in the league of underdeveloped countries. Thus; these obstacle need to be addressed from a glocalised approach.

Competing Interests

There is no financial interest or any other interest to declare herein which may have arisen from this research.

Funding

The researcher received no funding from any person, government and non-governmental agency for this research.

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